

Ultrasonic, volumetric and viscometric studies of ammonium ceric nitrate in aqueous solution at different temperatures

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Ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity of solutions of ammonium ceric nitrate in water at various concentrations have been measured at temperatures 313.15, 318.15 and 323.15 K. From the experimental data, various acoustical parameters are calculated. Some of these parameters are correlated with concentration. The results are interpreted in terms of molecular interactions occurring in the solution.

A literature survey reveals that while studying solvation of ions, thermodynamic and transport properties of alkali and tetra alkyl ammonium halides have been studied in water, heavy water, protic and aprotic solvents^{1,2}. However, ammonium salts were rarely studied. In continuation of our previous studies on thermodynamic, acoustic and transport properties of electrolytes in solutions³⁻⁶, the present paper deals with the measurement of ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity of aqueous solutions of ammonium ceric nitrate at 313.15, 318.15 and 323.15 K.

Results and discussion

From the experimental data on density, sound velocity and viscosity, various acoustical parameters such as specific impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (K_s), Rao's molar sound function (R_m), the Van der Waals constant (b), molar compressibility (W), intermolecular free length (L_f), relaxation strength (r), solvation number (S_n) etc. have been evaluated by the following standard equations :

$$\text{Specific impedance (Z) : } Z = U \rho$$

where U is the speed of sound and ρ is the density of solution.

$$\text{Isentropic compressibility (K}_s\text{) : } K_s = 1/(U^2 \rho)$$

$$\text{Rao's molar sound function (R}_m\text{) : } R_m = (M/\rho) U^{1/3}$$

where M is the molecular weight of solution.

$$\text{Van der Waals constant (b) : } b = \frac{M}{\rho} (1 - RT/MU^2 (\sqrt{1 + MU^2/3RT} - 1))$$

where R is gas constant and T is absolute temperature.

$$\text{Molar compressibility (W) : } W = (M/\rho) \kappa_s^{-1/7}$$

$$\text{Intermolecular length (L}_f\text{) : } L_f = K \cdot \kappa_s^{1/2}$$

where K is Jacobson constant ($= 6.0816 \times 10^4$).

$$\text{Relaxation strength (r) : } r = 1 - (U/U_\alpha)^2$$

where $U_\alpha = 1600 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

$$\text{Solvation number (S}_n\text{) : } S_n =$$

$$\frac{M_2/M_1 [1 - \kappa_s/\kappa_{s1}] [(100 - X)/X]}$$

where X is the number of grams of solute in 100 g of the solution and M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights of the solvent and solute respectively.

Some of these parameters are given in Table 1. Some parameters were also correlated with concentrations and the correlation coefficients along with correlation equations are given in Table 2. Table 2 shows that excellent linear correlation between some parameters and concentrations were observed.

Table 1 shows that ultrasonic velocity increases with concentration. The variation of ultrasonic velocity in a solution depends on the intermolecular free length on mixing. On the basis of Eyring and Kincaid⁷ model, U increases with decreasing intermolecular free length and vice versa at all the temperatures. In the present study, with increase in concentration of solute, intermolecular free length decreases at all the temperatures and hence there is increase in U and Z with concentration. This suggests the presence of solute-solvent interaction in the system. This is further supported by molar sound function (R_m), molar compressibility (W) and Van der Waal's constant (b), which increase linearly with concentration indicating thereby absence of complex formation. This causes adiabatic compressibility to decrease with increase in concentration of solute.

It is observed from Table 1 and Fig. 1 that initially, the increase in temperature causes an increase in velocity but then it decreases. This suggests that more increase in tem-

Table 1. Variation of acoustical parameters with concentration (c) at 313.15, 318.15 and 323.15 K

Conc. <i>M</i>	$U \times 10^5$ cm s^{-1}	$Z \times 10^5$ g cm^{-2}	$K_s \times 10^{-11}$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{dyn}^{-1}$	L_f Å	r	R_m	W	b	S_n	$\eta \times 10^3$ poise
313.15 K										
0.00	1.5204	1.5086	4.3598	0.4016	0.0970	968.21	547.935	16.4126	—	6.5295
0.01	1.5299	1.5195	4.3016	0.3989	0.0857	1126.90	637.639	19.1703	0.2012	7.0328
0.02	1.5347	1.5445	4.2188	0.3950	0.0799	1264.89	716.962	21.5848	0.3979	7.0223
0.04	1.5437	1.5687	4.1294	0.3908	0.0691	1554.22	881.930	26.6514	0.7936	7.0039
0.06	1.5452	1.5860	4.0805	0.3885	0.0673	1829.45	1039.54	31.5220	1.1888	6.9729
0.08	1.5489	1.5994	4.0365	0.3864	0.0628	2107.44	1198.40	36.4392	1.5896	6.9535
0.10	1.5521	1.6179	3.9821	0.3838	0.0589	2365.68	1346.93	41.0214	1.9846	6.9339
318.15 K										
0.00	1.5224	1.5075	4.3571	0.4015	0.0946	970.599	549.09	16.4471	—	5.9604
0.01	1.5310	1.5312	4.2659	0.3972	0.0844	1118.31	633.38	19.0013	0.1986	5.2427
0.02	1.5340	1.5495	4.2071	0.3945	0.0808	1258.95	713.98	21.4646	0.3953	5.3933
0.04	1.5378	1.5575	4.1752	0.3930	0.0762	1559.47	884.65	26.7455	0.7945	5.4286
0.06	1.5442	1.5742	4.1138	0.3901	0.0685	1847.76	1048.95	31.8172	1.1960	5.6297
0.08	1.5526	1.5931	4.0429	0.3867	0.0584	2129.94	1209.96	36.7753	1.5974	5.7467
0.10	1.5666	1.6224	3.9345	0.3815	0.0413	2398.13	1363.53	41.4455	1.9989	5.9260
323.15 K										
0.00	1.5168	1.4987	4.3990	0.4033	0.1013	971.544	549.55	16.4796	—	5.9228
0.01	1.5198	1.5263	4.3109	0.3993	0.0977	1110.27	629.43	18.9110	0.1987	5.9156
0.02	1.5242	1.5426	4.2530	0.3966	0.0925	1253.18	711.13	21.4134	0.3946	5.9924
0.04	1.5296	1.5544	4.2060	0.3944	0.0861	1549.46	879.62	26.6242	0.7947	6.1523
0.06	1.5344	1.5674	4.1580	0.3922	0.0803	1838.20	1044.15	31.7217	1.1943	6.2827
0.08	1.5366	1.5811	4.1160	0.3902	0.0777	2113.35	1201.62	36.6083	1.5944	6.3927
0.10	1.5422	1.5983	4.0568	0.3874	0.0710	2382.65	1355.89	41.3757	1.9868	6.5157

Fig. 1. (a) Variation of velocity with concentration. (b) Variation of molar sound function with concentration : (◆) 313.15, (■) 318.15 and (▲) 323.15 K.

perature causes solute-solvent interactions to break due to which inter molecular free length also increases as observed for 323.15 K in Table 1.

Table 2. The correlation coefficients (γ) and correlation equations between some acoustical parameters and concentrations (C) at different temperatures

Parameters (γ)	Correlation equation
313.15 K	
U (cm s^{-1})	$U + 0.2344 \times 10^5 C = 1.5303 \times 10^5$
Z (g/cm^2)	$Z - 1.0205 \times 10^5 C = 1.5199 \times 10^5$
K_s (cm^2/dyn^1)	$K_s + 3.3 \times 10^{-11} C = 4.3 \times 10^{-11}$
L_f (Å)	$L_f + 0.1566 C = 0.3987$
r	$r + 0.2828 C = 0.0852$
R_m	$R_m - 13813.29 C = 994.9101$
W	$W - 7916.358 C = 561.2217$
b	$b - 244.0462 C = 16.7891$
S_n	$S_n - 19.8288 C = 0.0015$
η (Poise)	$\eta + 0.0011 C = 0.0070$

(Table-2 contd.)

318.15 K		
U (cm s ⁻¹)	0.9741	$U + 0.3729 \times 10^5 C = 1.5210 \times 10^5$
Z (g/cm ²)	0.9858	$Z - 0.9261 \times 10^5 C = 1.5235 \times 10^5$
K_s (cm ² /dyn ¹)	0.9866	$K_s + 3.4 \times 10^{-11} C = 4.3 \times 10^{-11}$
L_f (Å)	0.9859	$L_f + 0.1613 C = 0.3988$
r	0.9734	$r + 0.4509 C = 0.0916$
R_m	0.9998	$R_m - 14301.22 C = 979.8635$
W	0.9999	$W - 8154.458 C = 554.428$
b	0.9998	$b - 250.9883 C = 16.5738$
S_n	0.9999	$S_n - 20.0183 C = -0.0042$
η (Poise)	0.9890	$\eta + 0.0072 C = 0.0052$
323.15 K		
U (cm s ⁻¹)	0.9893	$U + 0.2345 \times 10^5 C = 1.5190 \times 10^5$
Z (g/cm ²)	0.9935	$Z - 0.7448 \times 10^5 C = 1.5232 \times 10^5$
K_s (cm ² /dyn ¹)	0.9925	$K_s + 2.6 \times 10^{-11} C = 4.32 \times 10^{-11}$
L_f (Å)	0.9927	$L_f + 0.1232 C = 0.3997$
r	0.9895	$r + 0.2798 C = 0.0987$
R_m	0.9998	$R_m - 14192.17 C = 974.5897$
W	0.9999	$W - 8099.874 C = 551.8132$
b	0.9999	$b - 250.6427 C = 16.4925$
S_n	0.9999	$S_n - 19.9084 C = -0.0014$
η (Poise)	0.9976	$\eta + 0.0066 C = 0.0059$

Further, the solvation number is observed to increase linearly with concentration of solute. The positive values of solvation number indicate the structure forming tendency of the solute at all temperatures. Hence, occurrence of association of solute molecules with solvent molecules is confirmed.

Experimental

Double-distilled water was used for the preparation of solutions of different concentrations. Ultrasonic velocity (U), viscosity (η) and density (ρ) of these solutions were measured at different temperatures using M-82 multi-frequency interferometer operating at 3 MHz, suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer and by pycnometer, with an accuracy of $\pm 0.06\%$, $\pm 0.01\%$ and ± 0.0001 g/ml, respectively.

Fig. 2. (a) Variation of molar compressibility with concentration. (b) Variation of Van der Waals constant with concentration : (◆) 313.15, (■) 318.15 and (▲) 323.15 K.

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